

Influence of Safety Protocols on Job Satisfaction and Performance of a Company : A Case Study of Miro Forestry Company Ltd. in Mile 91, Sierra Leone

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ABSTRACT

Sierra Leone has a workplace safety law known as the 'Factories Act 1974' but very little has been done to address the issue of health and safety in the workplace. Improving workers' safety in Sierra Leone is challenging because of social, economic, literacy and political factors. Most workers in Sierra Leone industries are semiskilled and illiterate and have not completed a very high level of formal education.

This study was conducted to assess the impact of safety protocol on job satisfaction and company performance, of which the Miro Forestry Company in Mile 91 Sierra Leone was used as a case for the study. The study examined the management processes related to safety protocol and safety management system in the company, contributions of safety to performance; including the challenges affecting the implementation of safety protocols at workplace and factors that determine job satisfaction of employees and the effects on company performance. The sample size for the study was seventy-nine (79) staff members, chosen from a total population of one hundred (100), 20 management staffs (safety department), 50 sawmill staffs and 9 staffs from the pole treatment plant. Overall, the research planned to collect information from 79 respondents. The self-administered questionnaire with close-ended questions was used to collect data. Data was analyzed in both OriginPro 2024 and Microsoft Excel and presented in frequency tables, charts and descriptive narratives. The results showed a significant impact of safety protocol on job satisfaction and company performance. However, some challenges hindered the success of safety protocol in the Miro Forestry Company. It was recommended that staff should be trained and educated on safety protocol, company conforms to budget and workers be motivated.

Keywords: Safety protocol, job satisfaction, workplace safety, hazardous materials, compliance, company performance.

INTRODUCTION

Safety protocols within workplaces are critical for safeguarding employees and mitigating risks associated with their roles, as highlighted by Armstrong (2009). These protocols not only ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards but also significantly influence job satisfaction and organizational performance. Job satisfaction, a crucial determinant of employee well-being and productivity, revolves around the contentment individuals derive from their work, often influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic rewards as noted in management studies (Armstrong, 2009).

The implementation of effective safety measures, such as those observed at Miro Forestry Company Ltd. in Mile 91, Sierra Leone, plays a pivotal role in enhancing job satisfaction by minimizing occupational hazards and fostering a secure working environment. Research indicates that improved job satisfaction correlates with enhanced productivity, reduced turnover rates, and overall organizational success (Armstrong, 2009; Veltri, 2011).

The context of Sierra Leone, particularly within its burgeoning forestry sector exemplified by Miro Forestry, offers a unique setting to explore the interplay between safety protocols, employee satisfaction, and company performance. This study aims to contribute empirical insights into how safety management

systems influence organizational dynamics and employee welfare, aligning with global efforts to address occupational health challenges (WHO, 2024).

Central to this investigation is an in-depth analysis of safety management processes at Miro Forestry, examining their impact on operational efficiency and employee morale. By identifying challenges in safety protocol implementation and evaluating their implications on job satisfaction and organizational outcomes, this research seeks to inform strategic interventions that promote sustainable growth and enhance employee well-being in similar industrial contexts worldwide.

In conclusion, this study endeavors to enrich the scholarly discourse on workplace safety and its broader implications, offering actionable recommendations for improving safety cultures and optimizing organizational performance within the forestry sector and beyond.

Problem Analysis

The central research challenge addressed in this study pertains to workplace safety, despite ongoing efforts. In the context of modern technological advancements and increased use of hazardous chemicals, companies like Miro Forestry face heightened risks to the health and safety of employees and the public. A fundamental conflict exists between employers striving for output and efficiency and employees requiring protection and well-being in the workplace. If unaddressed, this conflict can result in substantial financial losses. Employees may allocate earnings toward treating job-related illnesses, injuries, or fatalities, while companies bear costs such as compensations, fines, and repairs stemming from workplace accidents and hazards.

Aim and Objectives

This study aims to contribute to the improvement of job satisfaction and company performance within the context of Miro Forestry Company in Mile 91, Sierra Leone.

Specifically, the research focuses on the following objectives: (1) Assess the management processes that demonstrate the company's commitment to safety. (2) Investigate the role of the safety management system in achieving overall company performance. (3) Identify the challenges hindering the effective implementation of safety protocols in the workplace. (4) Determine the factors influencing employee job satisfaction and their subsequent effects on company performance.

Literature Review

Zohar (2002) highlights the significant role of active management involvement in safety initiatives. His research demonstrates that policies, resource allocation, and personal behavior by management enhance safety compliance among employees. Similarly, Fernández-Muñiz, Montes-Peón, and Vázquez-Ordás (2007) conducted a study on Spanish industrial firms, revealing a direct correlation between management commitment to safety and the implementation of comprehensive safety programs and practices. Their findings indicate that firms with higher levels of management commitment exhibit superior safety performance metrics.

In a study of Indian chemical industries, Vinod Kumar and Bhasi (2010) explored the relationship between safety management practices and safety behavior. Their results suggest that companies with well-implemented Safety Management Systems (SMS) experience fewer accidents and incidents, leading to improved operational efficiency and reduced costs. Michael et al. (2005) examined the impact of SMS in manufacturing settings, finding that firms with comprehensive safety programs had significantly lower injury rates and higher productivity levels compared to those with less developed safety systems. These findings underscore the importance of structured safety management systems in enhancing overall company performance.

Hale and Borys (2013) reviewed the state-of-the-art in safety rule implementation, identifying common challenges faced by organizations. They found that limited financial and human resources, insufficient training programs, and a lack of management support are significant obstacles to effective safety protocol implementation. Similarly, Krause, Seymour, and Sloat (1999) investigated barriers to implementing behavioral safety programs and found that inadequate training and lack of management support were significant impediments. Their study suggests that addressing these challenges through comprehensive training and visible management support could improve safety outcomes.

Gyekye and Salminen (2007) investigated the impact of job satisfaction on safety behavior among industrial workers in Ghana. Their study found that higher job satisfaction levels correlate with better safety compliance and lower accident rates. Judge et al. (2001) conducted a comprehensive meta-analysis examining the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. Their findings confirm that higher levels of job satisfaction are associated with increased employee productivity, lower turnover rates, and better overall organizational performance.

Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman (1959) developed the two-factor theory of motivation, which posits that job satisfaction is influenced by motivators (e.g., recognition, work itself) and hygiene factors (e.g., working conditions, salary). Their research indicates that addressing both types of factors is crucial for enhancing job satisfaction and performance.

Clarke (2006) explored the relationship between management commitment and safety performance across various industries. His study concludes that visible and proactive management commitment, including regular safety meetings and inspections, positively correlates with reduced accident rates and enhanced safety compliance. Probst and Brubaker (2001) examined the influence of job insecurity on safety outcomes, finding that job insecurity is associated with lower safety compliance and higher accident rates.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 The study Area

Miro, a prominent commercial forestry and timber products group, is situated in Mile 91 – Royanka village within Sierra Leone's Tonkolili District. Specializing in plywood for regional and international construction markets, transmission poles for electrification, and timber panel products, the company manages expansive sustainable plantations covering more than 16,000 hectares. With a workforce of approximately 2,000 employees, Miro is currently expanding at an annual rate ranging from 1,500 to 3,000 hectares. Recent advancements include pilot-scale operations in veneer, sawmilling, and edge glue board production, marking a significant step towards enhancing its industrial timber products division. Future growth projections anticipate increased wood flows from plantations, driving further expansion in the coming years.

Figure 1: Map depicting the study area

3.2 Research Design

In this study, a descriptive quantitative technique was employed, allowing for the meticulous description and summarization of data through numerical and graphical means. This method involves the systematic collection and presentation of quantitative data, transforming complex information into easily interpretable formats such as charts, graphs, and tables. By offering a clear and concise representation of the data, this technique facilitates a comprehensive analysis, enabling researchers to discern patterns, trends, and relationships within the dataset. Consequently, it enhances the accuracy and reliability of the findings, supporting more informed conclusions and recommendations. This approach is particularly valuable in

providing a robust framework for data interpretation, ensuring that the results are both accessible and meaningful to a broad audience.

3.3 Study Population

The study aimed to gather insights from a diverse group of 79 respondents, carefully selected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the organizational dynamics. This cohort included 20 management staff from the safety department, offering a strategic perspective on safety protocols and policies. Additionally, 50 sawmill staff were included, representing the operational workforce directly involved in the core production processes, thereby providing practical insights into daily operations and challenges. Furthermore, 9 staff members from the pole treatment plant were also targeted, contributing specialized knowledge about this specific aspect of the production chain. By engaging respondents from these distinct groups, the study ensured a well-rounded and multifaceted analysis, capturing a wide range of experiences and viewpoints within the organization.

3.4 Sampling Design and Data Collection Procedure

Data for this study was obtained from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was directly collected from respondents using a semi-structured questionnaire and a key informant interview guide. Secondary data was sourced from various journals, publications, and online resources. This comprehensive approach ensured a robust foundation for the study and guided the researcher throughout the research process.

3.5 Sample Size

The sample size for this study was carefully determined to ensure that the data collected would be both representative and statistically significant. A total of 79 respondents were targeted, encompassing a diverse range of individuals from different departments and roles within the organization. This included:

- **Management Staff from the Safety Department:** 20 respondents were selected from this group. Their insights were crucial for understanding the strategic perspective on safety protocols and policies.
- **Sawmill Staff:** 50 respondents from this group were included to capture the operational workforce's practical insights into daily operations and challenges. Their perspectives provided a comprehensive view of the core production processes.
- **Staff from the Pole Treatment Plant:** 9 respondents from this specialized group were targeted to contribute their specific knowledge about the pole treatment aspect of the production chain.

The selection of these respondents was designed to ensure a balanced and inclusive sample that reflected the varied experiences and viewpoints within the organization. This diverse sample size facilitated a thorough analysis and interpretation of the data, enabling the researcher to draw well-rounded and robust conclusions.

3.6 Data Collected and Procedures

Upon gathering all relevant data from the selected sample, the researcher embarked on a meticulous process of classifying and summarizing the responses. This involved systematically organizing the data to ensure that it accurately reflected the information provided by the respondents. Each response was carefully examined and categorized to facilitate a structured analysis.

The analysis was conducted using advanced tools, specifically Microsoft Excel and OriginPro 2024. Microsoft Excel was utilized for its powerful data management and statistical analysis capabilities, enabling the researcher to perform complex calculations, create pivot tables, and generate descriptive statistics. This tool was instrumental in organizing large datasets and conducting preliminary analysis.

3.7 Data Analyses and Results

To further enhance the analytical process, OriginPro 2024 was employed. This software provided advanced graphical and statistical analysis functions, allowing for more sophisticated data visualization and

interpretation. With OriginPro 2024, the researcher could create high-quality graphs and charts that vividly illustrated the findings, making complex data more accessible and understandable.

The results of this comprehensive analysis were meticulously presented in a variety of tables and graphs. These visual representations were designed to clearly convey the key findings, trends, and patterns identified in the data. By using both numerical and graphical means, the researcher ensured that the presentation of results was both clear and compelling, facilitating a deeper understanding of the study's outcomes. This rigorous data analysis procedure not only enhanced the accuracy and reliability of the findings but also provided a solid foundation for drawing informed conclusions and making evidence-based recommendations.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

4.1 Summary of the Respondents Statistics

Analyzing the data from Figure 2, which outlines the distribution of respondents across different departments, we observe the following: The Safety Department includes 20 respondents, accounting for 25% of the total sample, indicating that about a quarter of the respondents are from this department.

Figure 2: Pie Chart showing Respondents Statistics

The Sawmill Department, with 50 respondents, represents 63% of the total sample, signifying a significant majority. The Pole Treatment Department has 9 respondents, making up 12% of the total, which is the smallest group among the three departments. Overall, there are 79 respondents, comprising 100% of the sample. The prominent representation from the Sawmill Department suggests that it is either the largest department within the organization or a primary focus of the study. In contrast, the Safety and Pole Treatment Departments are less represented, with the former having moderate and the latter the least representation. This distribution could impact the study's results, particularly if department-specific practices or conditions are being examined, as the substantial representation from the Sawmill Department might skew the overall findings. Therefore, it is crucial to consider this distribution when interpreting the study results and to be cautious about generalizing findings across all departments if there are significant disparities in representation.

4.2 Age (Years) distribution of respondents

Figure 3: Age (Years) distribution of respondents

In Figure 3, the age distribution of respondents reveals a diverse range of perspectives, with the largest group being those aged 26-35, making up 31.65% of the sample. This is followed by the 36-45 age group at 25.32%, and the 46-55 age group at 21.52%. These middle-aged groups, representing nearly 80% of the respondents, suggest a strong engagement or impact on individuals in their prime working years. The youngest group, aged 18-25, comprises 12.66% of the respondents, indicating lesser involvement from those in early adulthood, while the oldest group, 55 and above, accounts for 8.86%, reflecting a smaller representation of senior individuals. This distribution highlights the predominance of middle-aged respondents, providing valuable insights from those with substantial work experience, while also including younger and older perspectives for a well-rounded understanding of the study's subject matter.

4.3 Gender status of worker

Figure 4 illustrates the gender distribution of respondents, with 69 males (87.34%) and 10 females (12.66%). This analysis highlights a significant gender imbalance in the study sample, with a markedly higher representation of males. Such a disparity suggests that the findings may be more reflective of male perspectives and experiences, potentially limiting the study's overall generalizability and highlighting the need for a more balanced gender representation in future research.

Figure 4: Gender status of worker

4.4 Availability of safety protocols in the company

Figure 5 illustrates responses to the question regarding the availability of safety protocols in the company. According to the data, 56 respondents (70.89%) confirmed the existence of safety protocols, while 23 respondents (29.11%) reported their absence. This indicates that a majority of respondents are aware of and acknowledge the importance of occupational health and safety measures in their workplace. The high percentage of affirmative responses suggests a strong understanding and implementation of safety protocols. However, the significant minority reporting a lack of safety protocols highlights areas where improvements in safety awareness and implementation are needed.

Figure 5: Safety Protocol in the company

4.5 Contribution of safety protocol on employees’ performance

In Figure 6 below, respondents provided varied insights on the contribution of safety protocols to employees' performance. Ten respondents (12.66%) indicated that safety protocols reduce absenteeism, while twelve respondents (15.19%) believed these protocols enhance productivity. Thirty respondents (37.97%) stated that safety protocols improve company profitability, and fifteen respondents (18.99%) felt they boost employee satisfaction. Additionally, twelve respondents (15.19%) mentioned that safety protocols lower staff turnover rates. These findings underscore the perceived benefits of safety protocols, with a significant emphasis on their role in increasing productivity, enhancing employee satisfaction, and boosting company profitability. The data suggests that most respondents recognize the multifaceted advantages of implementing robust safety protocols in the workplace.

Figure 6: Contribution of safety protocol on employees’ performance

4.6 Factors affecting the implementation of safety protocol in the company

In Figure 1.6 above, the bar chart highlights the primary factors impacting workplace safety, with the high cost of training, providing protective gear, and compensating affected employees being the most significant challenge at 37.97%. This suggests that financial constraints are a major barrier, emphasizing the need for more cost-effective solutions or increased budgeting for safety measures. The low level of employee involvement, accounting for 31.65%, indicates a need for strategies to enhance engagement, such as involving employees in safety planning and decision-making. A powerless HR department, noted by 12.66%, suggests that strengthening the role and authority of HR could mitigate this issue. The absence of identified safety standards and legislation, at 11.39%, highlights the need for clear and enforced safety protocols. Although poor management support is the least frequent factor at 6.33%, it remains critical, as lack of support can undermine all other safety efforts.

Figure 7: Factors affecting the implementation of safety protocol in the company

To address these issues, organizations should explore cost-effective training programs, increase employee involvement, empower HR departments, establish and enforce safety standards, and ensure strong management commitment to safety initiatives. Addressing these factors can significantly improve workplace safety and employee well-being, leading to a more productive work environment.

CONCLUSIONS

The study was designed to analyze the impact of safety protocols on job satisfaction and company performance at Miro Forestry Company. It focused on several key areas, including management's commitment to safety, the contribution of safety management systems to company performance, challenges in implementing safety protocols, and factors influencing job satisfaction and company performance.

- **Management's commitment to safety:** The study found that 56.67% of respondents confirmed the existence of safety protocols at Miro Forestry Company. However, 43.33% felt these protocols were not effectively implemented, citing minimal employee involvement and a lack of protective tools as significant issues. Positive aspects noted included the presence of safety rules, policies, committees, and officers, along with a reduction in work-related diseases and accidents. Notably, 100% of respondents agreed on the need for stronger commitment to safety protocols.
- **Contribution of Safety Management Systems to Company Performance:** In terms of company performance, 40.00% of respondents indicated that safety protocols had increased productivity, while 13.33% noted an increase in company profits, and 16.67% observed higher employee satisfaction. Additional benefits included reduced injuries and deaths, enhanced cooperation between employees and management, and increased responsibility and awareness among employees.
- **Challenges in implementing Safety Protocols:** The study identified several challenges in implementing safety protocols. High costs associated with training, protective gear, and employee compensation were highlighted by 36.67% of respondents as major obstacles. Other challenges included individual carelessness and insufficient budget allocation.
- **Factors influencing Job Satisfaction and Company Performance:** Regarding job satisfaction and company performance, 73.33% of respondents expressed satisfaction with their job responsibilities, and 67.67% of supervisors were committed to quality, which positively impacted company performance.

- **General Conclusion:** The study concludes that safety protocols significantly contribute to increased production, profitability, and employee satisfaction at Miro Forestry Company. These protocols raise employee awareness and align the goals of management and employees. Additionally, respondents noted that safety protocols help reduce work-related injuries and deaths. The study suggests that improving training and education, ensuring management commitment, conducting safety drills, motivating employees, providing safety gear, and involving employees in decision-making will further enhance safety and company performance

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- There is a need to address the lack of specific knowledge and skills regarding safety by providing education and seminars. These initiatives will increase awareness and help achieve desired safety outcomes.
- Encouraging staff involvement and participation in decision-making processes is essential to foster a sense of belonging and attachment to the company. This involvement will make employees feel valued and appreciated.
- Recognizing the importance of motivation in ensuring compliance with safety protocols is crucial. Various motivational strategies, including allowances, should be used to create a safety culture within the company.
- It is recommended that Miro Forestry Company improve its safety management system by building human resource capabilities for employees and partners. Addressing the challenges identified in the study will ensure the health and safety of all stakeholders.

SUGGESTED AREA FOR FURTHER STUDY

Further research should examine the role of employee involvement and participation in enhancing motivation and management legitimacy in the workplace.

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